

Correlating Distribution Patterns of Intertidal Gastropods with Physicochemical Parameters along the Adri Coast of Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

The present study was carried out to assess the impacts of various physicochemical parameters on the distribution patterns of gastropod species in intertidal zone of Adri coast of Gujarat. Intertidal zones along the Adri coast are rocky and sandy, with small to large pools and puddles as well as rock crevices. Ecological attributes such as the density, abundance, and frequency of the common gastropod species were studied along with the physicochemical parameters of seawater. The result indicates that all the species have distinct spatiotemporal variations for different seasons in the different intertidal zones i.e. upper, middle, and lower

zones. Different physicochemical parameters are tolerated to some extent by the gastropod species. Both salinity and temperature specifies a direct positive correlation with the density, abundance, and frequency of intertidal gastropod species. Conversely, pH shows a moderately negative correlation with the distribution pattern and diversity attributes of gastropod species.

Keywords: *Gastropod, environmental factors, intertidal habitat, spatiotemporal distribution.*

Introduction

Molluscs are a diverse group of soft-bodied, ancient animals with a long history. They are second only to the arthropods as one of the animal kingdom's most diverse and species-rich phyla. Molluscs are widely distributed and have a large number of species, which means that they are important ecological components of both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems worldwide (Oehlmann and Oehlmann 2002). Mollusc species have been reported from about 80,000 to 100,000 worldwide. There are currently 5070 species of molluscs known to exist in India, 3370 of which are found in marine environments (Venkataraman and Wafer, 2005). Molluscs have

been favored in previous studies on rocky shores and intertidal zones because they are numerous, relatively slow-moving, and easy to identify (Benkendorff and Davis, 2002; Chiba, 2007; Benkendorff and Przeslawski, 2008). The class Gastropoda, a large taxonomic class within the phylum Mollusca, consists of snails and slugs (Bouchet et al., 2005). The largest species in the phylum of molluscs are gastropods, which have 10,000 species and have spread to nearly every continent (Ruppert et al., 2004; Strong et al., 2008). Furthermore, gastropods vary morphologically in relation to their surroundings. Individuals of the same species on the identical rocky shore may have different morphologies as a result of different

microhabitats (Wolf et al., 1997). The distribution of gastropod species is influenced by abiotic (dissolved oxygen, temperature, salinity and pH) and biotic factors (Jeje and Fernando, 1986). Benthic diversity is regulated by a multitude of ecological factors, including dissolved oxygen, temperature, salinity, sand, and organic matter; no single factor can be regarded as an ecological master factor (Pathak and Abido, 2014).

The organisms inhabit different vertical heights on rocky shores according to their thermal niches, which are set by tolerance limits for abiotic factors (Prusina et al., 2014). The diversity of gastropoda in Indian waters was found to be significantly impacted by the physical and chemical characteristics of the waters (Sharma et al., 2013). Gastropods are highly correlated with the physical, chemical, and biological factors that affect living things, such as temperature, salinity, pH, oxygen content, and sediment texture (Pyron and Brown, 2016). Gastropod growth and continuity are completely dependent on various physicochemical stresses, in which temperature has a greater effect on the distribution of organisms due to desiccation. The fluctuations in environmental parameters associated with tide create the intertidal zone, which is more vulnerable and extreme than any environment. Because of this, intertidal organisms encounter more rapid fluctuations in the degree of physicochemical factors (Dave and

Chudasama, 2018; Rao and Ganpati, 1971). Many researchers have studied on correlation in Gujarat (Bhadja and Kundu, 2012; Vandarwala et al., 2020; Bharda et al., 2020; Dodiya and Poriya, 2023). The present study focused on analyzing the spatiotemporal variations of gastropods in different intertidal zones and the impacts of physicochemical parameters on the gastropod species of the Adri coast of Gujarat.

Materials and Method

The present study was conducted from August 2022 to July 2023 along the Adri coast, located at 20°96'07" N latitude and 70°27'94" E longitude, situated on the Kathiawar peninsula in Gujarat, India (Figure 1). The Adri coast features various intertidal habitats, including rocky outcrops that are sprinkled with sand. Gastropod species were identified with the help of standard taxonomic keys and taxonomist. The quadrat sampling method was used to study distribution patterns of intertidal gastropod. A 0.25 m² quadrat frame was systematically placed at 20 meter intervals in three (upper, middle, and lower) intertidal zones using stratified random sampling to assess the gastropod population, with data recorded for three ecological attributes: density, abundance, and frequency. Calibrated digital instruments were used to measure physicochemical parameters such as salinity, pH, and temperature.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Site - Adri coast, Gujarat

Result and Discussion

The present study correlates distribution patterns of intertidal gastropods with physicochemical along the Adri coast of Gujarat. The Adri coast features various intertidal habitats, including rocky outcrops that are sprinkled with sand. The upper, middle, and lower intertidal zones are rocky-sandy, while the supratidal zone is covered in sand. Gastropods and *Ulva lactuca*, a type of green seaweed, are the main inhabitants of the upper zone. Sponge, zoanthids, gastropods, other molluscs, crabs, barnacles, worms, and green and brown seaweeds predominate in the middle zone, which is made up of numerous tiny tide pools and

fissures. The lower zones are characterized by large tide pools and a flat substratum that is home to brittle stars, gastropods, barnacles, worms, *Zoanthus* colonies, and other macrofauna living in algae cover.

Over the period from August 2022 to July 2023, the highest seawater temperature (35°C) was recorded in March, and the lowest seawater temperature (27°C) was recorded in January (Figure 2). pH levels varied between 7.1 and 8.6; the minimum value and maximum value were reported to be in April and November, respectively (Figure 2). Salinity levels ranged from a minimum (28 ppt) in December to a maximum (35.5 ppt) in March (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Monthly Variations in Physicochemical Parameters Along the Studied Adri Coast

During the study period, gastropod species were frequently found in association with seaweed. A total of 48 species of gastropods were reported. Figure 3 displays information on the density of gastropods during the period of August 2022 to July 2023 in three distinct zones: the upper, middle, and lower zones. In the upper zone, the highest gastropod density was recorded in December, May, January, and March, and the lowest density was recorded in February, April, and June. January recorded the highest density in the Middle Zone, indicating a significant population of gastropod species (Figure 3). The

lowest density was observed in August, September, October, February, May, and July, all with a density suggesting periods of decreased population (Figure 3). In January, the highest density of gastropod species was reported. The lowest gastropod density was recorded in June. The density value of gastropods ranged from 0.1 no/ 0.25 m² to 7.2 no/ 0.25 m² reported during the study period (Figure 3). These observations suggest seasonal fluctuations in density across the different zones over the specified time period, with some months having higher

populations and lower numbers of gastropod species in specific zones than others.

Figure 3. Monthly Variations in Density (no/ 0.25 m²) of Studied Gastropod Species Along the Adri Coast

Abundance in the upper zone varied throughout the months. Maximum abundance was reported in January, while minimum abundance was noted in March in the upper zone (Figure 4). Generally, the upper zone maintained moderate to high levels of gastropod abundance compared to other zones. In the Middle Zone, abundance varied as well. The highest abundance occurred in May, suggesting a substantial increase in the gastropod population during that month (Figure 4). The lowest abundance was reported during the months of November, December, April, June, and July (Figure 4). The Middle Zone

exhibited the highest variability in abundance compared to the other zones, with several months showing notably low levels (Figure 4). Abundance in the lower zone, with fluctuations observed across the months. January had the highest abundance in the lower zone, indicating a significant presence of gastropods during that time. The months of August, October, December, March, and June had the lowest abundance (Figure 4). During the study, abundance values varied from 1.1 no/0.25 m² to 7.8 no/0.25 m².

Figure 4. Monthly Variations in Abundance (no/ 0.25 m²) of Studied Gastropod Species Along the Adri Coast

Frequency of gastropods in the upper zone varies by month. The range of frequency (8% to 90%) of the gastropod species that have not existed in uniform showed more or less fluctuation during all months. The month of December exhibited the highest frequency in the upper zone, indicating that gastropods were present in significant numbers that month (Figure 5). Significant peaks include those in February and January (Figure 5). The months of October, November, April, and June were those with the lowest frequency (Figure 5). The months with the highest frequency were January, May, and June in the middle zone (Figure 5). The lowest frequency occurred in October. In the

lower zone, July has the highest frequency (Figure 5). January and September also show a relatively high frequency. November has the lowest frequency (Figure 5). Overall, the data demonstrates dynamic fluctuations in gastropod frequency across all three zones over the specified months. There are observable frequency peaks at certain intervals and relatively low levels at other times. Seasonality, habitat suitability, and environmental conditions are the factors that may have an impact on these variations. The geomorphological and physical characteristics of the research sites may be connected to this variation in habitats (Wilson 1990).

Figure 5. Monthly Variations in Frequency (%) of Studied Gastropod Species Along the Adri Coast

Correlation Analysis between Gastropods and Physicochemical Parameters

Spatial distribution of molluscs varied between shores, perhaps as a result of their combined morphological, physiological, and behavioral adaptations (Ali et al., 2019). Ecological attributes such as density, abundance, and frequency were assessed using the quadrat method. The correlation analysis was represented to illustrate the interrelationship between the physicochemical parameter and the population dynamics of gastropod species. Ecologically, the correlation between biotic and

abiotic factors is significant (Lwin et al., 2020). The present research reported the changes in population dynamics of the gastropod species that existed under the effect of the physicochemical parameter. Examining the relationship between intertidal organisms and physico-chemical parameters offers valuable insights into how abiotic factors influence biological life (Bharda et al., 2020).

The correlation matrix chart shows the relationship between the ecological attributes (density, abundance, and frequency) of gastropod species and the physico-chemical

parameters. In this chart, different circle sizes and colours represent positive and negative correlations between physicochemical parameters and ecological attributes. The small, light red circle indicates a negative correlation. A tiny, light blue circle that indicates a moderately positive correlation; a big, dark red circle that has a slight negative correlation. A big, dark blue circle that is small indicates a somewhat moderate positive correlation; very large, dark blue circles signify a strong, positive correlation. Very large, dark red circles show a strongly negative correlation.

Figure 6. Correlation of Gastropods Density with Physicochemical Parameters

The physicochemical parameters affect the population density of gastropods. Environmental factors like temperature, salinity, pH, wave action, and other physical constraints have a direct effect on the distribution patterns and population of gastropods (Khouw, 2006). The population density of gastropods displays a moderate positive correlation with temperature and a strong positive correlation with salinity, while exhibiting a slight negative correlation with pH (Figure 6). The growth and survival of gastropods are entirely dependent on a variety of physico-chemical stresses, with temperature having a greater impact on organism distribution because of desiccation (Balamani, 1996). Specifically, there is a moderately positive

correlation with temperature, indicating that warmer conditions tend to support higher populations. Additionally, a strong positive correlation with salinity suggests that increased salt levels in the habitat positively impact gastropod populations. The slight negative correlation with pH suggests that more acidic conditions may adversely affect gastropod populations.

Figure 7. Correlation of Gastropods Abundance with Physicochemical Parameters

The population of gastropod abundance exhibits a somewhat positive correlation with salinity and a highly positive correlation with temperature; there is also a somewhat positive correlation with pH (Figure 7). The second most significant physical factor of the marine environment is thought to be salinity. This salinity factor has a big impact on the fauna (Sampath kumar and Kannan, 1998). The positive correlation between gastropod abundance and salinity suggests that gastropods thrive in higher salinity environments due to their physiological adaptations. Similarly, the strong positive correlation with temperature indicates that gastropods survive in favourable conditions.

The somewhat positive correlation with pH implies that while gastropods can tolerate moderate pH fluctuations, it has a lesser impact on their abundance compared to salinity and

temperature. Gastropod frequency demonstrates a moderately positive correlation with temperature and a highly positive correlation with salinity, whereas it exhibits a strongly negative correlation with pH (Figure 8). Gastropod frequency is positively associated with both temperature and salinity, indicating that higher temperatures and salt levels support an increased gastropod population. Molluscs had a negative correlation with every other environmental factor and a positive correlation with salinity, sand, and temperature (Jayaraj et al., 2007).

Figure 8. Correlation of Gastropods Frequency with Physicochemical Parameters

Conversely, there's a strong negative correlation with pH, signifying that acidic conditions lead to a decrease in gastropod frequency. The coast selected for this study had not been extensively explored previously for species diversity or the impacts of physicochemical parameters on gastropod species. The correlation analysis study found that physical and chemical factors significantly influenced gastropod diversity (Vandarwala et al., 2020). The present study gives details about the effects of physicochemical parameter on distribution of intertidal gastropods along the rocky coast of the Adri coastline.

Conclusion

The present study provides details about the distribution of intertidal gastropods in the different intertidal zones on the rocky coast of the Adri coastline. The Adri coast provides a unique habitat with rocky-sandy substrate for the gastropod population. The gastropod species shows different level of tolerance for different physicochemical parameters. Temperature and salinity have a direct positive effect on the density, abundance, and frequency of intertidal gastropod species. While a negative correlation was observed between density, abundance and pH that shows a moderate effect on the distribution pattern and diversity of gastropod species in different zones and different habitats at the coast. Findings of present study indicate that physicochemical parameters, along with different microhabitats, drives the distribution patterns of gastropod populations.

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